

COMPACTION AND MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF AFP COMPOSITES WITH FIBER TOW GAPS: EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION AND MULTIPHYSICS MODELING

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Introduction

- **Automated fiber placement**
 - High degree of control over complex layup designs
 - Design flexibility
 - Optimized fiber orientation which can provide tailored strength/stiffness
 - Improved material utilization
 - Reduced labor needs leading to potential cost savings
- **Features of AFP deposited preform**
 - Fiber tow gaps and overlaps
 - Large non-linear deformation
 - Irregular morphology upon cure and compaction: **ply waviness** and **non-uniform thickness**
 - Voids/resin-rich regions
- **Significance**
 - Potential knock-down in mechanical properties
 - Need to predict failure for a given combination of deposited features

AFP layup process of thermosetting composite for manufacturing complex shape structures

Unidirectional prepreg layup by AFP

Microstructural Features

ply waviness

Void

Resin rich region

non-uniform thickness

Resin rich region

Fereidouni, M. and Hoa, S.V., 2025. In-situ consolidation of thermoplastic composites by automated fiber placement: Characterization of defects. *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, 38(2), pp.471-511.

Resin Bleed-out and Squeeze Flow

Resin Bleed-out: Occurs when excess resin flows out of a composite laminate during the curing process

Squeeze Flow: Resin is forced inward under pressure, filling gaps

When Squeeze Flow Occurs: During the **compaction stage** of curing

Microstructural Effect: Squeeze flow yields resin-rich regions

Jamora, V. C., Rauch, V., Kravchenko, S. G., & Kravchenko, O. G. (2024). Effect of Resin Bleed Out on Compaction Behavior of the Fiber Tow Gap Region during Automated Fiber Placement Manufacturing. *Polymers*, 16(1), 31. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym16010031>

Resin Bleed-out: Chemo-rheological Behavior

- Unidirectional tow compaction experiment
- Material: IM-7/8552
- Cure cycle: Manufacturer's recommended cure cycle

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \frac{K \alpha^m (1 - \alpha)^n}{1 + \exp [C (\alpha - (\alpha_{C0} + \alpha_{CT} T))]}$$

- Effect of temperature of flowability of the resin during the cure cycle

$$\mu(T, x) = \mu_{01} \exp\left(\frac{E_1}{RT}\right) + \mu_{02} \exp\left(\frac{E_2}{RT}\right) \left(\frac{x_g}{x_g - x}\right)^{A+Bx+Cx^2}$$

Characterization of Resin Bleed-out

- Interrupted cure cycle was used to record the progression of resin bleed-out and prepreg squeezing

$$\bar{\rho}_P^{(T)}(t) = \frac{A^{(T)}_1}{\left(1 + e^{\frac{A^{(T)}_2 - t}{A^{(T)}_3}}\right)}$$

$$\bar{\rho}_P^{(L)}(t) = \frac{A^{(L)}_1}{\left(1 + e^{\frac{A^{(L)}_2 - t}{A^{(L)}_3}}\right)}$$

Characterization of Resin Bleed-out: Experimental Results

- Longitudinal bleed-out flux is 4x higher than transverse bleed-out flux due to higher permeability in the fiber direction
- Fiber volume fraction rises rapidly with small ϵ_{33} (0-3%) to 0.61 and plateaus after that.

$$V_f(\epsilon_{33}) = V_{f_0} + B_1 * e^{\left(\frac{-B_2}{\epsilon_{33}}\right)}$$

Process modeling

Jamora, V. C., Rauch, V., Kravchenko, S. G., & Kravchenko, O. G. (2024). Effect of Resin Bleed Out on Compaction Behavior of the Fiber Tow Gap Region during Automated Fiber Placement Manufacturing. *Polymers*, 16(1), 31. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym16010031>

Constitutive Model

- Temperature dependent hyper viscoelastic compaction simulation:

$$\hat{\sigma} = \hat{\sigma}^e + \hat{\sigma}^v$$

- Hyper elastic Neo-Hookean behavior in 2-3 plane

- Elastic behavior in fiber direction:

$$\sigma_{11}^e = 2\mu_f \varepsilon_{11} + \lambda_f \text{tr}(\varepsilon)$$

- Viscous response due to strain rate dependence, tow geometry and microscopic fiber effects

$$\sigma_{ij}^v = \eta_{rate_{ij}} \cdot \eta_{ply_{ij}} \cdot \eta_{micro_{ij}} \cdot \hat{\dot{\varepsilon}}_{ij}$$

- Tensorial approach was used for $\eta_{rate_{ij}}$ which show that the viscosity is anisotropic and it is dependent on fiber volume

- Fiber orientation is updated based on deformation gradient

- Variable fiber volume fraction for updating ply viscosity term

Capturing Bleedout-Squeeze Flow Coupling in AFP Composites

- The amount of bleed out resin is determined based on the gap surface area, which allows to predict amount of resin flow into the gap.
- Gap is experiencing closing due to ply sinking.
- To capture this effect, sequential modeling is performed:
 - First squeeze flow is performed, which determines the gap closure behavior.
 - Then, the time of resin filling the gap is determined: given by instance when resin inflow reaches the gap volume during squeeze flow simulation.

Capturing Bleedout-Squeeze Flow Coupling in AFP Composites

$$V_{Res}(t) = \frac{\bar{\rho}_P^{(T)}(t) \cdot SA_{Gap}}{\rho_r}$$

- Resin rich region forms when bleed-out resin volume equals tow gap void volume
- Predicted gap filling time from squeeze flow simulation: $t_{fill}=26$ min
- Predicted time of gap filling with resin pressure: $t_{fill}=28$ min
- Observation from experiment $t_{fill}=29$ min
- Resin pressure activation give more consistent result with experiments

Benchmark 1: Compaction Modeling of Embedded Tow Gap

Benchmark 2: Compaction Modeling of Staggered Gaps

Benchmark 2: Progressive Failure Analysis for Staggered Gap Samples

* Units are in mm.

Benchmark 2: Knock-down in Mechanical Properties

Benchmark 2: Surface Strain Analysis

PR_x

GAP_x

- PR_x: uniform strain field at failure
- GAP_x: strain concentration around the corner of the initial gap where fiber waviness is located

Benchmark 2: Failure Mode Analysis

Benchmark 2: Failure Mode Analysis

Cohesive zone damage

Cohesive zone damage

- Delamination failure initiates near the resin rich region located near the top and bottom surface.

Benchmark 2: Failure Mode Analysis

Conclusion

- Compaction modeling scheme was developed using multi-physics FEA that captured the real morphology in AFP composites
- Coupling between the squeeze flow and bleed out was shown to be critical in capturing the resin rich region and associated fiber waviness
 - The proposed approach was demonstrated for simple gap (Benchmark 1) and staggered gap (Benchmark 2)
- The simulated cured morphology of AFP composites were used for PFA of Benchmark 2 case
- The results revealed close agreement between the failure modes and strength knockdowns on one side and the morphology of cured composite
 - The locations of resin rich region and fiber waviness interact with the failure modes observed in pristine sample configuration

THANK YOU!

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